

Proceedings of the Meeting of the Board of Studies (BOS) in Civil Engineering held on 4th October, 2021 at 11.00 am at the Office of Civil Engg HoD, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru.

Members Present:

- Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde (HOD and Chairman BOS) ✓
- Mr. Shrinath Rao K. (Member) *K. Shrinath Rao*
- Mrs. Shilpa S. *SS*
- Mr. Prasanna P. Rao *PPR*
- Mr. Deekshith K. *DK*

Members Absent:

- Dr. K S Babunaryan
- Mr. Shyam Bhat M

Agenda: Modification in the syllabus of B.Tech programme as per NEP 2020 and Review of Scheme for B.Tech Civil Engineering.

1. Discussed about the possibilities of modifying the contents of Scheme and Syllabus for B.Tech Civil Engineering programme as per the requirements of NEP 2020 and also to cater the needs of the industry. It was decided to further communicate with industrial experts regarding the same.
2. The Scheme and Syllabus of B.Tech Civil Engineering programme was discussed and few changes were suggested by the Chairperson of BOS to improve the quality of the proposed programme in line with the guidelines of NEP 2020.
3. It was also suggested to incorporate hand-on based Certification Courses, Swayam etc for the 3rd and 4th year students.

As there were no other points to be discussed, the meeting was concluded at 12.15 pm.

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde,
Chairperson

Proceedings of the Meeting of the Board of Studies (BOS) in Civil Engineering held on 27th May , 2019 at 11.00 am at Conference Hall, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru.

Members Present:

- Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde (HOD and Chairman BOS)
- Dr. Nagaraja A. (Member)
- Mr. Shrinath Rao K. (Member)

Members Absent:

- Dr. K S Babunarayan
- Mr. Shyam Bhat M

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde, Chairperson of the BOS in Civil Engineering welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for the discussion and the following modifications are made and agreed by the BOS.

Agenda

Modification in some sections of THE REGULATIONS GOVERNING B. TECH. PROGRAMME – 2017 (Full Time) for the faculty of Engineering

Existing

R.6.0 Enrolment Requirement

R.6.1 There shall not be any restriction for promotion from an odd semester to the next even semester, provided the student has fulfilled the attendance requirement

R.6.2 A student shall be eligible for promotion from an even semester to the next odd semester (i.e. of the next academic year) if the student has not failed in more than five heads of passing of the immediately preceding two semesters and has passed in all the subjects of all the lower semester examinations. A theory or practical shall be treated as a head of passing.

Illustrations

- A student seeking eligibility to 3rd semester should not have failed in more than 4 heads of passing of first and second semesters taken together.
- A student seeking eligibility to 5th semester should have passed in all the subjects of 1st and 2nd semesters and should not have failed in more than 4 heads of passing of third and fourth semesters taken together.

c. A student seeking eligibility to 7th semester should have passed in all the subjects up to 4th semester and should not have failed in more than 4 heads of passing of 5th and 6th semesters taken together.

Modified

6.0 Enrolment requirement

6.1 There shall not be any restriction for promotion from an odd semester to the next even semester, provided the student has fulfilled the attendance requirement

6.2 There shall not be any restriction for promotion from an even or odd semester to next semester, provided the student has fulfilled the attendance requirement applied to full duration of the course.

But for these all other section remains the same.

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde,

Chairperson

Proceedings of the Meeting of the Board of Studies (BOS) in Civil Engineering held on 22 July, 2018 at 11.00 am at Conference Hall, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru.

Members Present:

- Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde (HOD and Chairman BOS)
- Dr. Nagaraja A. (Member)
- Mr. Shrinath Rao K. (Member)

Members Absent:

- Dr. K S Babunarayan
- Mr. Shyam Bhat M

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde, Chairperson of the BOS in Civil Engineering welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for the discussion.

Agenda-1: Discussion and Acceptance of subjects and Syllabus for the Ph.D program in Civil Dept.

Since the department is providing the PhD programme, a meeting was called to discuss about the subject to be included for the mandatory coursework for the same.

Following are the minutes of the meeting

1. Discussion was done to select the course work subjects which will be very useful to the candidates to build a strong theoretical base for the literature study and the appropriate problem definition.
2. It was decided to include the Research Methodology as one of the subject to promote the systematic and scientific outcome based procedures in the research work , including the latest guidelines given by the SU and AICTE/UGC.
3. Detailed syllabus to be included in each course work subject also discussed and decided, considering the candidates chosen area of Research.

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde,

Chairperson